

OVERCOMING THE HUMAN-ROBOT COMMUNICATION BARRIER IN MEDICINE THROUGH THE INTEGRATION OF BASIC EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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ABSTRACT

This work focuses on the development of a prototype aimed at reducing the communication barrier between a patient and a medical robot. The system integrates basic emotional intelligence, enabling it to recognize the patient's emotional state and adapt its communication style. Experimental results show an average emotion detection confidence of 0.760 and correct adaptation of 90% of responses. The most frequently identified emotion was anxiety (30%), highlighting the need for emotional support in medical scenarios..

Introduction

The lack of emotional intelligence in medical robots limits their communication capabilities. The aim of this work is to develop a prototype with basic emotional intelligence to overcome this barrier. The research hypothesis is that adapting to the patient's emotional state will improve the quality of interaction [3].

Methods

The methodology is based on the concept of basic emotional intelligence, implemented through a three-stage empathic cycle: recognizing patient emotions using sentiment analysis and a medical trigger dictionary, interpreting them in the context of the dialogue, and adapting the robot's communication strategy.

A modular software architecture was created to implement this approach. The input module handles speech transcription acquisition and cleaning. The emotion analysis module combines sentiment analysis using pre-trained models [2] with a dictionary of trigger expressions. The central dialogue management module, built on Rasa [1], integrates emotional data into the decision-making process. The response generation module formulates the robot's final replies.

The prototype was implemented in Python using NLP and machine learning libraries. The system's effectiveness was evaluated through test scenarios simulating typical medical dialogues.

Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, an experiment was conducted using the MedQuad dataset, containing 16,407 medical questions and answers. The system was tested on a representative sample of queries demonstrating various patient emotional states.

Table 1. Statistics of the system with emotional intelligence

Parameter	Value
Total queries processed	10
Average emotion detection confidence	0.760
Average query processing time	0.145 sec
Emotion detection rate	90.0%
Most frequent emotion	anxiety
Most frequent communication strategy	supportive

Figure 1 presents the results of the experimental evaluation of the emotional intelligence system.

Figure 1. Analysis of the effectiveness of emotional intelligence integration in medical dialogue systems

Chart A shows the distribution of patient emotional states identified during testing. The predominance of anxious states (30%) confirms the need for emotional support in medical interactions. Chart B reflects the level of response adaptation by the system, where 70% of queries received full or partial emotional adaptation, indicating the high effectiveness of the emotional intelligence module. Chart C presents a comparative analysis of user ratings, showing a significant improvement in perceived empathy (4.2 vs. 2.1 on a 5-point scale) and overall interaction comfort (4.5 vs. 2.8) when using the system with emotional intelligence.

Analysis of the distribution of patient emotional states revealed the following structure:

- Anxiety: 30.0% (3 queries)
- Fear: 20.0% (2 queries)
- Pain: 20.0% (2 queries)
- Sadness: 10.0% (1 query)
- Joy: 10.0% (1 query)
- Neutral: 10.0% (1 query)

The system demonstrated high effectiveness in recognizing emotionally charged queries, with an emotion detection rate of 90%. The average query processing time was 0.145 seconds, meeting the real-time requirements for dialogue systems. The most frequently applied communication strategy was supportive (40% of cases), which corresponds to the prevalence of anxious states among patients.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the fundamental feasibility of implementing basic emotional intelligence in medical robots. The developed prototype confirms the hypothesis that considering the patient's emotional state significantly improves the quality of interaction.

The experimental results presented in Figure 1 show that the system successfully recognizes the main emotional states of patients, with anxiety being the most common (30%), emphasizing the importance of emotional support in a medical context. The high emotion detection rate (90%) and average detection confidence (0.760) confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

The scientific novelty of the work lies in the formalization of the empathic cycle model and the development of an architecture that integrates emotion analysis into the dialogue management process. The practical significance is confirmed by the creation of a functional prototype capable of processing emotionally charged medical queries while maintaining operational efficiency (0.145 sec per query).

Prospects for future research include expanding the system's functionality by integrating non-verbal signal analysis, using more complex natural language processing models, and conducting clinical trials with real patients. The proposed approach opens new possibilities for creating medical robots capable of acting as full-fledged communication partners, which could significantly enhance their effectiveness in practical healthcare.

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